

TYPES OF MENTAL WEAKNESS IN CHILDREN AND METHODS OF PREVENTION

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Abstract. This article provides information on types of mental retardation in children and methods of prevention. Mentally retarded refers to a steady decline in mental, first of all, intellectual development as a result of organic damage to the brain. Mentally retarded children will not be able to master the program of general education schools. Children with severe mental retardation cannot acquire knowledge and skills at school.

Key words: mentally retarded, clinical-psychological, defect, cognitive activity, mental, attention, process, etiology, mother, pregnancy, injury, oligophrenia, endogenous, exogenous, postnatal, passive.

Cognition is the leading deficit in the clinical-psychological picture of mental retardation is that the activity has not developed. Cognitive impairment thinking operations, speed of mental processes, impaired mobility, attention, manifested in the underdevelopment of memory and a number of cortical functions will be.

The etiology of mental retardation varies. Mental retardation of the fetus in the mother's womb, at birth or during the early development of the central nervous system due to genetic disorders, injuries, asphyxia, infections, intoxications originates.

The clinical description of the main forms of mental retardation is closely related to the pathogenesis of the injury, the time of the negative impact.

The causes of oligophrenia are different. Oligophrenia according to etiological signs divided into two main groups:

1. Oligophrenia caused by endogenous (genetic) effects, connected with hereditary pathology or present in the family or appearing for the first time in this individual;
2. Oligophrenia caused by exogenous influences (infections, intoxications, brain traumas in early stages of fetal or postnatal ontogenesis).

In the origin of oligophrenia, polygenic type of heredity is also unique importance is given. Pathological genetic factors passed down from parents accumulation occurs.

The exogenous form of oligophrenia includes cases in which the nerve external negative to the child's brain during the period of pregnancy to underdevelopment of the system causes effects.

These include various chronic diseases during embryonic and fetal periods (toxoplasmosis, syphilis, etc.). others) and acute (rubella, influenza, epidemic parotitis,

infectious hepatitis, rash smallpox, etc.) forms of oligophrenia caused by infectious diseases during the mother's pregnancy are included. Poisoning of the mother's body with alcohol, chemicals, as well as some drugs (antibiotics, sulfonamides, barbiturates, quinine, hormones, etc.) also causes oligophrenia. Radioactive and X-ray radiation also have a pathogenic effect on the fetus and the cells of the parents. Various endocrine diseases in the mother (diabetes, thyroid, glandular, pituitary injuries) also play a pathogenic role. Toxicosis during pregnancy, vitamin imbalance also has a negative effect.

Chronic in the mother's cardiovascular system, lungs, liver and kidneys deficiencies lead to pathology of the fetus. Incompatibility of the blood of the mother and the fetus in terms of the rhesus factor also leads to negative consequences.

Prolonged lack of oxygen in the fetus before birth (hypoxia) affects the formation of the brain.

The time of exposure is also important in fetal damage. The first three months of pregnancy are very dangerous important aspects are the formation of the brain.

Exogenous forms of oligophrenia are the beginning of the central nervous system infections, intoxications and injuries during development (up to 1.5-2 years).

Variants of mental deficits associated with resulting injuries are also included. In these cases, meningitis of various etiologies, encephalitis, meningoencephalitis, severe somatic diseases (measles, scarlet fever, parotitis, dysentery, etc.), intoxication of the nervous system (postvaccinal encephalitis) cause oligophrenia. Special attention should also be paid to postnatal brain injuries. Hydrocephalus plays an important role in the pathogenesis of such injuries.

Oligophrenia according to the degree of manifestation of intellectual deficiency divided into four levels: light, medium, heavy and deep.

Mild mental retardation. Light, able to concentrate and has a good mechanical memory children with mental retardation will receive education in a special (correctional) program possible This program is based on concrete and demonstrative methods, mathematics.

It makes learning writing, reading and other subjects much easier, therefore for a child can occupy it for 9 years. Later, the child acquires professional knowledge can work independently.

Children with mild mental retardation acquire speech skills a little late, most of them use speech for everyday purposes, able to master the skills of maintaining and participating in conversation will be However, their speech has phonetic distortions and vocabulary limitation, lack of understanding of words, the meaning of the words used it is typical that it will not be clear. Words are not fully used as a means of communication.

Active vocabulary lags behind passive vocabulary. A weak-minded person understands more than he speaks. Active vocabulary is not only limited, but also filled with stamps (identical word combinations). Phrases are simple, uniform, violations in the grammatical construction of speech (connection of words in sentences) are manifested in the lack of connectives and auxiliaries. There are difficulties in expressing one's thoughts, telling what one has read and heard. In some cases, signs of underdevelopment of speech are observed.

The limited and slowed senses of sight, hearing, kinesthetic, tactile, smell and taste (sense) make the environment difficult. Poorly developed perception makes it difficult for a mentally retarded person to form an accurate picture of himself and the things that surround him.

Memory is characterized by slowness and sluggishness, quick forgetting. But memory may be stored and well formed. Usually subject and only external features of reality are remembered. Internal logical connections memories about and explaining in words creates great difficulties.

Free activity of mentally retarded persons, weakness of aspirations, initiative.

It is distinguished by its lack, stubbornness, weakness of social and personal motives.

Necessary decisions are often made on a short-circuit basis. Actions insufficiently goal-directed, impulsive, there is no struggle of motives. In many cases of mild mental retardation, which does not require abstract thinking, it is possible to engage in unskilled and semi-skilled manual labor based on practical activities. They are carpenters, tailors, embroiderers and they learn other professions.

Moderate mental retardation. Moderate mental retardation with lack of formation of cognitive processes is described. Thinking is concrete, there is no sequence. In this category of persons understanding and use of speech develops behind (with a delay of 3-5 years), and full development in this area is limited. Often speech is accompanied by gross defects. Vocabulary is small, it consists mostly of words and phrases used in everyday life.

Almost all children with this level of mental retardation have movements coordination, accuracy and speed will be disturbed. Movements are slowed down, clumsy, this prevents the formation of the running mechanism and learning to jump. Children with mental retardation, even as teenagers, have difficulty entering a given movement state and cannot hold it for more than a few seconds. They have difficulty moving from one action to another. The lack of development of movement in some of them is manifested in the uniformity of movements, their slow pace, sluggishness, and discomfort. In others, excessive mobility is manifested in inconsistency with the goal, disorder, uncoordinated actions.

People with moderate mental retardation have a lot of information and imagination less. The formation of scattered concepts is completely absent or sharply limited.

Development of perception and memory is observed.

Autistic symptoms or other general developmental disorders in children can appear. Some of them are kind and polite.

Others - angry, angry. Still others are stubborn, liars, lazy, tend to do impulsive (unexpected) things.

Mental retardation often affects limbs, paws, fingers, head, skin, internal organs, (is accompanied by disorders in the development of genitals, teeth, face, eyes, ears.

Adults with moderate mental retardation require normal, competent supervision under constant supervision and guidance, taking into account their individual and personal qualities.

They can do work that they don't do (especially those who are busy with agricultural work where there are). People with moderate mental retardation will need social protection and support.

Severe mental retardation. In severe mental retardation, thinking is not only very concrete, rigid, but also is not formed at all from the ability to generalize. In most of them underdevelopment of motor functions, coordination disorders, etc

co-existing pathologies are clearly manifested. These individuals have great difficulties in self-service skills with. Some of them even use buttons and laces they can't even learn to tie.

Self-service education for children with severe mental retardation is limited to practicing skills and learning to find a target in the environment, developing communication. Speech has agrammatisms, defects in pronunciation of sounds, word wealth is low and not enough to organize any activity.

It is important to remember that this is a severe form of underdevelopment children who are sick can use it later in similar situations they need to repeat what they are being taught several times in order for them to understand and develop the skills they have.

Usually, intellectual disorders are obvious neurological pathologies: paralysis, paresis goes along with They include the skeleton, skull, limbs, skin and internal organs dysplastic body structure is observed.

People with this pathology require constant help and support. Profound mental retardation. It is understanding or carrying out requests or instructions in children

ability is limited. They have not developed attention, perception, memory. Think about it elementary processes do not exist. Most of the time, you don't understand the meaning of speech they use sounds or words that they do not understand the meaning of.

Most of such children have severe motor disorders, they completely immobile or the movements are sharply limited, urine and feces they cannot hold, they can only be communicated with in a rudimentary form. They can't take care of their basic needs, or this feature is very weak, and they need constant help and support.

Needs and actions are very simple, action reactions are irregular, not directed to the goal, stereotyped moving from side to side, agitation without external cause is observed.

The most severe of them do not cry, do not laugh, do not recognize the people around them. None nothing can attract attention. They have difficulty aiming in space. They are only affected by pain. The facial expression is meaningless. They cannot distinguish between what can be consumed and what cannot be consumed. They do not understand speech and gestures. Affects of anger, a desire to harm oneself are observed.

However, when working with such children, they are sensitive to sound, bright light, etc attention to color, moving objects and other influencers it is possible to achieve some achievements in education.

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